

D1.9

MAA Interim Evaluation Report

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
AGFT	AGFUTURA Technologies
AgKu	Agri Kulti Nonprofit Ltd
APRI	Asociación Aprisco de Las Corchuelas
CoWs	Cooperation Workshops
Dx.x	Deliverable
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
GA	General Assembly
JHI	The James Hutton Institute
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
MAWs	Multi-Actor Workshops
Mxx	Month
PS	Pilot Study
QH	Quadruple Helix
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

Background to the legumES project

The legumES will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumES;
3. that the ES benefits and cost offered by legumES are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, legumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising legumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The legumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multiactor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumES use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, legumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based Pilot Studies which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumES, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumES-project.eu

Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D1.9 – MAA Interim Evaluation Report*, presents an interim assessment of the implementation of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) within the legumES project at Month 26 (M26), February 2026. The report focuses in particular on the development and functioning of existing and emerging Living Labs (LLs), which constitute the primary structures through which the MAA is operationalised in legumES.

The evaluation is designed as a formative and reflective exercise, providing a snapshot of current practices rather than a summative assessment of performance or impact. It aims to support learning, identify strengths and development needs, and establish a baseline for the final evaluation to be conducted in August 2027 (Month 44) in Deliverable D1.1, using the same framework to enable comparison over time.

At project level, the report documents MAA-related activities implemented across work packages (WPs), including participatory, co-creation, and stakeholder engagement actions, based on inputs collected from WP leads. These activities demonstrate that the MAA is embedded across the project through a variety of formats, such as Multi-Actor Workshops, participatory trials, cooperation workshops, innovation-oriented events, and capacity-building actions.

At LL level, the evaluation applies a structured self-assessment framework based on the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) macro–meso–micro model. Self-assessment questionnaires were completed by LL host organisations. The questionnaire template is provided in Annex 2. The assessment examines governance and strategic orientation (macro level), project portfolios and operational capacity (meso level), and co-creation activities, stakeholder engagement, and iterative processes in real-life settings (micro level). The interim findings highlight a high diversity of LL maturity levels within legumES. Some LLs demonstrate advanced levels of development, with established governance structures, strong stakeholder engagement, and systematic application of co-creation processes. Other LLs are in consolidation or pilot stages, combining active experimentation with ongoing efforts to formalise governance, business models, and operational structures.

Support from WP1 capacity-building actions, including LL trainings, governance guidance, shared evaluation tools, and cross-LL learning, plays a central role in supporting LL maturation. In parallel, ongoing legumES activities provide practical opportunities to embed project activities within LL contexts as the project progresses.

Overall, the findings presented in D1.9 will serve as a reference point for monitoring progress and assessing change in LL maturity, governance, and co-creation practices in the final evaluation in August 2027.

Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

The legumES project aims to enhance the valorisation of ES provided by legumES across European agri-food systems through a strong emphasis on co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and real-life experimentation. Central to this approach is the implementation of the MAA, which seeks to ensure that relevant actors from science, practice, policy, business, and civil society are actively involved throughout the research and innovation process. This deliverable, **D1.9 – MAA Interim Evaluation Report**, presents an interim assessment of the implementation of the MAA within the legumES project at the interim stage of the project (February 2026). Within legumES, the MAA is operationalised primarily through LLs and Pilot Studies (PSs). PSs serve as thematic and territorial entry points for research and innovation activities, while LLs provide a more structured, long-term framework for co-creation, experimentation, and learning in real-life settings. Some PSs build on pre-existing LLs, while others are expected to progressively evolve into LLs during the project.

This report has two main objectives:

- **To document MAA-related activities implemented across the project**, including participatory and co-creation actions carried out within and across WPs. These activities are described as part of the overall MAA implementation and as opportunities for stakeholder engagement, without constituting a full evaluation of project-wide impacts.
- **To assess the current status of LLs** within the project, examining their level of development, functioning, and application of key MAA principles such as stakeholder involvement, co-creation processes, and governance arrangements.

The scope of this report is intentionally differentiated. A detailed self-assessment is applied to existing and emerging LLs, while a project-level overview documents the implementation of MAA-related activities across the project. Overall, this deliverable provides a structured overview of the current state of LL development and Multi-Actor engagement within legumES. It supports internal reflection, contributes to project learning, and informs subsequent evaluation activities planned for later stages of the project.

1.2. Interconnection to other Deliverables

This deliverable is closely linked to **D1.1 – MAA Periodic Evaluation Report**, which will provide the final evaluation of LL development at the end of the project. D1.9 serves as an interim reference point, documenting the current status of existing and emerging LLs at Month 26. The findings presented in D1.9 establish a baseline for comparison with later stages of the project, enabling the monitoring of progress in LL development, co-creation processes, and governance structures over time. The same evaluation logic and self-assessment framework will be applied in D1.1, allowing changes in maturity and implementation to be traced consistently.

In this way, D1.9 and D1.1 together form a coherent evaluation sequence, supporting continuity in monitoring and reflection throughout the project lifecycle.

Conceptual and Methodological Framework

2.1. Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)

The MAA is a strategic approach that ensures Research and Innovation (R&I) processes are inclusive, practice-oriented, and impact-driven. It promotes responsible R&I by integrating scientific excellence with real-world relevance, fostering solutions that are not only robust but also co-created, widely applicable, and societally meaningful. It encourages the active and meaningful involvement of all relevant actors throughout the entire lifecycle of an R&I project.

In Horizon Europe, the Multi-Actor Approach is defined as:

“a form of responsible R&I [that] aims to make the R&I process and its outcomes more reliable, demand-driven, shared and relevant to society. It also aims to have these outcomes shared more extensively. This entails more than just widely disseminating a project’s results or listening to the views of a board of stakeholders. A multi-actor project ensures the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic.”

— Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2023-2025: Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment, p. 21. [\[1\]](#)

At its core, the MAA fosters co-creation, knowledge sharing, collaborative decision-making, and shared ownership of results. It enhances the relevance and uptake of innovations by ensuring they are grounded in real-world needs and shaped by the people who will ultimately apply them. In legumES, the MAA is applied as a guiding principle to ensure that R&I activities are informed by, and carried out together with, relevant stakeholders from across the legume value chain and wider agri-food system. The MAA is operationalised through a combination of LLs, PSs, and a set of participatory and co-creation activities implemented across the project. The operationalisation of the MAA includes a range of concrete activities, such as Multi-Actor Workshops (MAWs), Participatory Farmer Research Trials, Cooperation Workshops (CoWs), innovation-oriented events, and capacity-building activities etc. These formats enable relevant stakeholders to contribute to problem identification, co-design of solutions, experimentation, and joint reflection. At the same time, they support knowledge exchange and the development of communities of practice across different regions and thematic areas. Through this combination of structures and activities, the MAA in legumES is embedded in both the design and implementation of project actions. The approach allows for differentiated levels of engagement, recognising that not all partners or contexts operate as LLs, while still ensuring meaningful opportunities for actor involvement across the project.

2.2. Living Labs (LLs)

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) describes LLs as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings.” [\[2\]](#) The EU Missions framework defines LLs as “user-centred, placebased and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems.” [\[3\]](#). Both definitions emphasise multi-actor collaboration, co-creation, and experimentation in real-life contexts as defining

features of LLs, which form the conceptual basis for the evaluation framework applied in this deliverable.

LLs are adopted in legumES as structured environments for implementing the MAA and facilitating the co-creation, testing, and validation of legume-based innovations in real-life contexts. Given the project's focus on ES valorisation, regional value chain development, and stakeholder-driven experimentation, LLs provide an appropriate framework to connect research activities with practical implementation and societal relevance.

In legumES, several core components of the LL approach are particularly important. First, multi-actor collaboration ensures that farmers, advisors, researchers, value-chain actors, consumers, and policy representatives jointly contribute to identifying barriers, testing solutions, and shaping strategies for legume production and consumption. Second, experimentation in real-life settings, including participatory farmer trials and regional workshops, enables the contextual validation of ES assessments and innovation pathways. Third, structured governance and iterative learning processes support long-term sustainability and the progressive maturation of LL configurations across partner regions.

These components form the conceptual foundation for the LL evaluation framework applied in this deliverable, which assesses LL development across macro (governance and constellation), meso (projects and capacities), and micro (activities and co-creation processes) levels.

2.3. Evaluation Objectives

The evaluation objectives of this report are defined at two complementary levels: **project level** and **LL level**. This distinction reflects the different roles that MAA activities and LLs play within the legumES project, allowing for a differentiated and proportionate evaluation.

LegumES operates at two interrelated levels of action. At project level, partners implement individual activities such as workshops, meetings, and thematic exchanges. While these activities contribute to stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange, they do not in themselves constitute LLs. LLs refer to broader, structured implementation processes embedded within defined ecosystems and governance arrangements. The LL assessment therefore focuses on the development and functioning of these structured configurations rather than on isolated project activities.

2.3.1. Project Level

At the project level, the evaluation focuses on how the MAA is embedded across activities implemented within and across WPs. The objective is to document and review MAA-related activities as part of the overall project implementation.

Specifically, the project-level evaluation aims to:

- Identify and review MAA-related activities implemented across WPs, including participatory and co-creation formats planned or carried out during the project.
- Examine the nature of stakeholder involvement in these activities, with attention to whether diverse participants are engaged as actors (i.e. co-creators contributing actively to processes and decisions) or as stakeholders (i.e. informed or consulted participants).

- Monitor progress toward planned engagement activities, documenting which activities have been implemented, who has been involved, and which activities are foreseen for later stages of the project.
- Identify areas where MAA implementation could be strengthened, such as the diversity of actors involved or opportunities for broader participation across WPs.

2.3.2. LL Level

At the LL level, the evaluation focuses on how existing and emerging LLs are functioning in practice as according to the principles of the MAA and core LL elements. In particular, the evaluation examines LLs as on-the-ground, practical tools that provide real-life environments and concrete spaces for co-creation, experimentation, and joint learning among actors. This level of evaluation, therefore, considers not only formal structures but also how LLs operate in day-to-day practice as settings where actors collaborate, test solutions, and reflect on results. The Living Lab-level evaluation aims to assess:

- Relevance and stakeholder diversity, examining whether LLs engage a balanced and relevant mix of actors and whether key actor groups are actively involved.
- Co-creation processes, assessing the extent to which LLs apply participatory approaches such as joint problem definition, co-design of solutions, experimentation, and shared learning.
- Governance and facilitation, focusing on transparency, inclusiveness, role clarity, and shared decision-making within LL structures.

This is an interim evaluation that provides a snapshot of LLs' functioning in February 2026. A final assessment of LL development and maturity will be carried out in **D1.1 – MAA Periodic Evaluation Report in August 2027**, allowing changes over time to be examined.

2.4. Evaluation Methods

2.4.1. Project Level

At the project level, the evaluation focuses on documenting the implementation of MAA-related activities across WPs over the course of the project, providing an overview of participatory and engagement activities implemented within and across WPs. The project-level evaluation is conducted interim overview in February 2026 and will be updated in the final evaluation in August 2027. Its purpose is to capture the current status of MAA-related activities, indicate progress against planned engagement actions, and provide a consolidated reference point for later comparison. The focus is on what activities have been implemented or prepared, who has been involved, and how actor engagement is addressed at project level.

Rather than applying a detailed assessment framework, a structured tracking approach is used. Specifically, the project-level evaluation is implemented through an overview table organised per WP, which records:

- 1) the main MAA-related activities planned or implemented within each WP,
- 2) the types of stakeholders involved (e.g. practitioners, researchers, value-chain actors, policy actors),

- 3) the nature of their involvement (e.g. information, consultation, active participation), and
- 4) the intended engagement goals of the activities.

D1.9 establishes a structured baseline of stakeholder participation across legumES. Deeper analysis and elaboration of influence and outcome-level effects will be conducted in the final evaluation (D1.1) in August 2027.

2.4.2. LL level

The progress of LLs within legumES is systematically monitored throughout the project duration, up to August 2027. The evaluation framework foresees **two assessment points**:

- An interim assessment in February 2026 (D1.9), and
- A final evaluation in August 2027 (D1.1).

To establish a structured starting point for LL development, a **baseline survey** was conducted among legumES PSs at the beginning of the evaluation process. The purpose of the survey was to assess their familiarity with the LL concept, their current engagement with LL-related practices, and their interest in formally developing or transitioning into a Living Lab structure. The survey assessed:

- self-reported familiarity with the LL concept,
- current involvement in LLs or LL-like activities,
- the existence of LL strategies or structures within pilot projects,
- and interest in formally establishing a Living Lab.

The detailed findings of this baseline survey are presented in *Section 3.1 (Baseline Findings)*. This baseline provides an overview of the initial landscape of LL readiness within legumES and forms the foundation for the evaluation approach applied in this deliverable.

Differentiated Evaluation Approach

Given the varying levels of familiarity, readiness, and interest in LL development identified through the baseline survey, a differentiated evaluation approach is applied at LL level. Partners that have expressed clear interest in developing a LL and/or have already integrated LL elements into their activities are included in the full LL self-assessment, structured across macro, meso, and micro levels. Partners that indicated uncertainty or no current intention to establish a LL are considered to be in an LL-exploration phase. For these partners, the interim evaluation relies on:

- baseline survey results, and
- documentation of their participation in MAA-related activities at project level.

This approach ensures proportionality and methodological consistency, while allowing partners to progressively structure LL practices over time. Their status will be revisited in the final evaluation in August 2027.

Assessment Logic and Analytical Levels

The February 2026 assessment captures the current maturity and stage of development of participating LLs, particularly in relation to governance, stakeholder engagement, and co-creation practices, to enable comparison over time. The August 2027 evaluation will provide a final assessment,

capturing the evolution and overall development of LLs over the project duration. These assessments will ensure continuous monitoring and refinement of the LLs, optimising their sustainability and impact over time.

The assessment covers key elements of a LL as defined by the ENoLL. The evaluation is structured across macro, meso, and micro levels of the LLs, ensuring a comprehensive and multi-dimensional assessment of the LL's progress.

- 1) At the **macro level** (The LL constellation), the focus is on the LL's overall orientation and strategic direction, including its organizational structure, partnerships, and governance frameworks.
- 2) At the **meso level** (LL projects), the evaluation shifts to the operational core of the LL, focusing on the specific projects it is running and/or participating in. This includes assessing the LL's strategies for achieving its mission and vision, as well as its capacities and resources.
- 3) Finally, the **micro level** (LL activities) concentrates on the activities within the LL itself, focusing on the deployment of specific methodologies and tools. It evaluates the effectiveness of the tools and techniques used by the LL to facilitate collaboration, experimentation, and learning.

For assessing and evaluating the progress of LLs, three distinct formats are used, each designed to track different aspects of development:

1) Scale Questions (Developmental Progress)

These questions use a scale to assess how the LL progresses towards higher levels of development. The goal is to move to a more advanced stage of maturity, with progress reflected in the upward movement along the scale.

2) Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs are used to set targeted numbers or measurable outcomes that the LL aims to achieve. These indicators provide specific, quantifiable goals, and progress is measured by how closely the LL is reaching or exceeding these targets.

3) Increased Participation or Involvement (Progress by Count)

In this format, progress is demonstrated by an increased number of marked items in the evaluation. The goal is for the LL to show an increased level of involvement or application of certain practices, tools, or stakeholder participation by the end of the project.

Project Level Evaluation

This chapter provides an overview of MAA-related engagement activities implemented across the project, including the types of engagements carried out, the stakeholders reached, and the main outcomes of these activities. It covers both activities that have already been implemented up to February 2026 and those planned within the project framework, thereby offering a comprehensive picture of how the MAA is operationalised in legumES. Together, these activities provide further insight into the scope, diversity, and progression of stakeholder engagement across WPs. The chapter also highlights challenges encountered in the implementation of the MAA.

Table 1. Project-Level Overview of MAA-Related Activities

WP	Activity Type	Activity Name	Implementation Status (at M26): Completed / Ongoing / Planned (not yet started)	Brief Description of Activity (Purpose & Scope)	Stakeholders Involved	Number of Stakeholders Engaged / Planned to Engage	Nature of Involvement (Consult / Involve / Collaborate)	Role of Stakeholders	Key Outcomes / Results (achieved and expected)	Challenges in Engagement
1	Workshop	National Multi-Actor Workshops (MAWs)	Completed	Workshops held in partner countries to identify barriers and opportunities for regional legume value chains and prioritise ecosystem services using SWOT analysis.	Farmers, processors, advisors, researcher, policymakers	278 (total across workshops)	Consult	Diverse stakeholders provided input and feedback through structured workshop discussions. They jointly identified and prioritised ecosystem services linked to legumES, contributed regional knowledge through SWOT analysis, and co-developed future-oriented scenarios and drivers of change	Eleven National MAWs were conducted across partner countries. The workshops resulted in: prioritised ES associated with legumES at regional level; SWOT analyses identifying key ES for valorisation; identification and ranking of social, technological, environmental, economic, and policy drivers of change; and an overall understanding of regional barriers and opportunities	Uneven participation across stakeholder groups

WP	Activity Type	Activity Name	Implementation Status (at M26): Completed / Ongoing / Planned (not yet started)	Brief Description of Activity (Purpose & Scope)	Stakeholders Involved	Number of Stakeholders Engaged / Planned to Engage	Nature of Involvement (Consult / Involve / Collaborate)	Role of Stakeholders	Key Outcomes / Results (achieved and expected)	Challenges in Engagement
									for valorising legume production and consumption	
1	Co-creation event	National Tasting-Co-creation Workshops (TaCos)	Planned / Ongoing	Consumer-focused workshops combining tasting, cooking demonstrations, and surveys to gather feedback on legume consumption, perceptions, and behavioural drivers, informing co-created demand-side strategies	Consumers		Involve	Feedback providers, co-creators	Consumer insights collected; input for demand-side strategies	Reaching diverse consumer groups and motivating active participation

WP	Activity Type	Activity Name	Implementation Status (at M26): Completed / Ongoing / Planned (not yet started)	Brief Description of Activity (Purpose & Scope)	Stakeholders Involved	Number of Stakeholders Engaged / Planned to Engage	Nature of Involvement (Consult / Involve / Collaborate)	Role of Stakeholders	Key Outcomes / Results (achieved and expected)	Challenges in Engagement
1/2	Trial	Participatory farmer trials	Ongoing	On-farm trials of legume crops in real-world farming conditions to monitor the ecosystem services provided by legumES and increase farmer capacity in ES monitoring	Farmers, agronomists	42 farmers (14 partners, 3 per partner)	Collaborate	Co-design and carry out field trials to collect data on the ecosystem services associated with legume crops	Datasets from farm trials, increased ES monitoring capacities	Typically working with the most engaged / innovative farmers, who might not be representative of the farming community
1	Focus groups	Consumer focus groups	Planned and to be executed between Feb and March 2026	Focus group discussions with consumers to understand perspectives on food systems, perceptions of legumES, and	Consumers	6 consumers per focus group, 8 focus groups planned. Therefore 48 consumers	Consult	Provide insight into consumer perceptions, challenges, and needs. Feedback used to inform survey development	Consumer insights collected; input for demand-side strategies.	Representative data collection across partner countries – focus groups to be held in only 4 partner countries

WP	Activity Type	Activity Name	Implementation Status (at M26): Completed / Ongoing / Planned (not yet started)	Brief Description of Activity (Purpose & Scope)	Stakeholders Involved	Number of Stakeholders Engaged / Planned to Engage	Nature of Involvement (Consult / Involve / Collaborate)	Role of Stakeholders	Key Outcomes / Results (achieved and expected)	Challenges in Engagement
				recognition of legume ES's.						(Portugal, Spain, Hungary, Switzerland)
WP 1	Workshop	Co-operation workshop	Completed	Workshop with actors in legume value chain	producers, researchers, farmers.	50-55	involve	Provided insights on ecosystem services, home grown legume-based products, balancing ecosystem services, reaching consumers, establishing hun initiatives, valorising ecosystem services.	Insights collected about improving ecosystem services establishment across legume value chain.	Representation, more researchers and less producers and manufacturers
WP 7	Delphi Study	Delphi Study-policy	Completed	Gather valuable information on the assessment and balancing of ecosystem services	Farmers, agronomists, Processors		Consult	Share perspective on: (1) the impact of the incentives/instruments that are currently available for legume production/consumption; and (2) what else	Generate policy recommendations - Shared November 2025	Complete responses to challenging questions

WP	Activity Type	Activity Name	Implementation Status (at M26): Completed / Ongoing / Planned (not yet started)	Brief Description of Activity (Purpose & Scope)	Stakeholders Involved	Number of Stakeholders Engaged / Planned to Engage	Nature of Involvement (Consult / Involve / Collaborate)	Role of Stakeholders	Key Outcomes / Results (achieved and expected)	Challenges in Engagement
				provided by legumES.				is required to support the wider production and use of legumES grown in national food systems?		
WP 4	Focus group format workshop	ADOPT workshops	Completed	Constraints and drivers of adoption were explored using the ADOPT tool in online workshops in three PS areas, namely Brandenburg in Germany, Pomurje in Slovenia, and Cacéres in Spain, with 6–10 key stakeholders per site.	Farmer (or representative), Farm advisor, Researcher, Policy advisor, Industry representative	6–10 key stakeholders per PS area	Consult	By actively engaging stakeholders to elicit expert-informed insights into local constraints, decision-making processes, and behavioural patterns, the workshops strengthened the foundation of the forthcoming ABM and ensured that simulated adoption pathways are firmly grounded in the practical realities of European legume-based farming systems.	The ADOPT workshops yielded key insights into how farmer behaviour and structural conditions influence the diffusion of legume-based innovations across the three pilot areas. While regional differences exist, common patterns emerged, notably moderate profit orientation, high risk aversion, limited investment flexibility,	Varying time and resource restrictions of the participants

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									and context-specific constraints that will inform the subsequent agent-based modelling.	

The overview presented above provides a consolidated picture of MAA-related activities implemented and planned across the legumES project. The overview indicates that the MAA is embedded across the project through a variety of engagement formats, including workshops, pilot activities, co-creation processes, and stakeholder consultations. Actor involvement spans multiple categories, including researchers, practitioners, value-chain actors, and policy representatives, reflecting the cross-cutting nature of the MAA within legumES.

In this deliverable, stakeholder involvement is assessed not only in terms of stakeholder categories, but also according to the *nature of involvement* in MAA-related activities. Three levels of engagement are distinguished: *Consult*, *Involve*, and *Collaborate*.

- “Consult” refers to stakeholders who are informed or asked to provide feedback, without participating directly in decision-making or co-creation processes.
- “Involve” refers to stakeholders who participate in activities and contribute input to ongoing processes.
- “Collaborate” refers to stakeholders who actively engage in co-creation, testing, experimentation, or joint decision-making processes.

In line with this distinction, stakeholders engaged at the “Collaborate” level can be considered active actors within the MAA framework.

The overview of MAA activities at the project level indicates that, in several WPs, stakeholder engagement is closely linked to PS implementation activities, including participatory on-farm legume trials, consultations, and co-creation formats such as workshops and focus groups, through which farmers, consumers, advisors, researchers, and policy actors contribute to experimentation, contextual validation, and structured knowledge exchange. In cases where engagement extends beyond consultation and involves active collaboration in experimentation and co-development processes, stakeholders function as active actors within the MAA.

LL Evaluation

3.1. Baseline Findings

This chapter presents the findings from the survey conducted among legumES PSs, focusing on their familiarity with the concept of LLs and their interest in becoming a LL. The survey assessed their self-reported familiarity with the LL concept, current involvement in LLs, and interest in establishing an LL based on their respective pilot projects. Respondents were asked to rate their familiarity (Figure 1) with the LL concept. Some pilot studies reported being very familiar with the concept, indicating an advanced understanding of the LL framework. Other pilots had only a slight or moderate familiarity, suggesting the need for additional capacity-building efforts. To ensure knowledge-transfer about the LL concept, and to ensure PS leaders are trained in using the LL approach a series of trainings is planned (See Annex 1).

Figure 1: Familiarity with the LL concept.

A key focus of the survey was determining whether PS were **interested in formally transitioning into an LL** (Figure 2). The responses showed that several pilots expressed strong interest in becoming an LL, some were partially interested, and a few indicated they were not currently considering this transition.

Figure 2: Interest in formally establishing a LL.

As for the last point, the survey gave us insights into whether pilots were **already operating as LLs** (Figure 3) or had integrated **elements of the LL strategy** into their work (Figure 4). Responses indicated that a few pilots had already incorporated some LL **principles**, describing themselves as "partially" functioning LLs, others were not yet considered LLs but were open to exploring the approach further.

Figure 3: Operating as a LL.

Figure 4: LL Strategy in place

This initial assessment of legumES pilot studies' knowledge and interest in adopting the LL model provides a valuable baseline understanding of the current landscape. The survey results highlight varying degrees of familiarity with LL principles, as well as diverse levels of interest and readiness to transition into an LL framework. While some PS have already incorporated elements of LLs, others are in the early stages of exploration, emphasising the need for targeted training and capacity-building efforts to facilitate the adoption of LL methodologies.

3.2. Existing and Emerging LLs

Within legumES, partners are at different stages of readiness and interest with regard to LL development. To reflect this diversity, a differentiated approach is applied in this interim evaluation.

Partners that have expressed clear interest in developing a LL and/or have already integrated LL elements into their activities are included in the full LL self-assessment. For these cases, the assessment examines the current functioning and development of LL elements in line with the evaluation framework described in Section 2.3. The intention is to monitor their progress over time, with the expectation that the number of partners engaging in full LL assessment may increase by the end of the project.

A second group of partners indicated uncertainty ("I don't know" or "Partially") regarding their interest in establishing a LL or indicated no interest in developing a LL ("No"). These partners are considered to be in an LL-exploration phase. For these partners, the interim evaluation relies on:

- baseline information derived from the LL survey, and
- documentation of their participation in MAA-related activities at project level (Table 1).

At this stage, these partners are not requested to complete the full LL self-assessment. However, they may actively contribute to MAA-related activities and may later decide to further develop LL structures, supported by capacity-building and training activities foreseen in WP1. Their status will be revisited in the final evaluation at in August 2027.

3.3. LL Assessment

This chapter presents the interim assessment of existing and emerging LLs within the legumES project, conducted in February 2026, based on a structured LL self-assessment questionnaire. The purpose of this assessment is to capture the current status of LL development, functioning, and application of MAA principles, rather than to evaluate performance or rank LLs against one another.

The self-assessment questionnaire was completed by the host organisations of each LL, reflecting their own understanding and experience of how the LL currently operates. The questionnaire is designed as a reflective and developmental tool, allowing LL hosts to assess their progress across key dimensions of LL development, including governance, collaboration, operational capacity, co-creation processes, and stakeholder engagement. Responses therefore reflect the status as of February 2026, including elements that are already in place as well as those that are still under development or planned.

The assessment framework follows the ENoLL macro–meso–micro structure, distinguishing between:

- the macro level, focusing on the LL constellation, governance, strategy, and business model;
- the meso level, addressing LL projects, operations, resources, and organisational capacity; and
- the micro level, examining LL activities, user and stakeholder engagement, and the quality of iterative co-creation processes in real-life settings.

The self-assessment questionnaire Template is provided in Annex 2. The present chapter synthesises and interprets these inputs in narrative form for each LL, translating questionnaire responses into a structured interim assessment. This approach ensures consistency across LLs while allowing differences in maturity, scope, and operational context to be explicitly acknowledged.

As this is an interim evaluation, the findings presented here represent a snapshot in time. The same self-assessment framework will be reapplied in the final evaluation (Deliverable D1.1) in August 2027, enabling structured comparison over time and supporting continuous learning, reflection, and further development of LLs within the legumES project.

3.3.1. ITC

Table 2: LL Assessment Results – ITC (February 2026)

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	Green Point F2F Living Lab
Host Organisation	ITC Murska Sobota
Geographical Location	Pomurje region, Slovenia
Sector(s) of Focus	Agri-food systems, Farm-to-Fork (F2F), sustainable and circular food systems, legumES and plant-based proteins, food loss and waste reduction, digital traceability and decision-support tools
Main Mission of the LL	To co-create, test and scale sustainable farm-to-fork solutions within the regional agri-food system, with a focus on legumES and plant-based foods for human consumption. The Living Lab integrates farmers, processors, retailers, consumers, researchers and public actors to pilot agroecological practices, processing and market innovations, digital tools, and governance models that strengthen resilience, sustainability and local value creation.
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENoLL) 	Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENoLL)
Living Lab Assessment	
Macro-level Assessment: Governance and LL Constellation	
<p>At the macro level, the Green Point F2F Living Lab demonstrates a high level of maturity in governance and strategic orientation. A shared vision and mission are clearly defined and actively guide LL activities. Core governance elements, including a governance structure, strategic decision-making processes, and an operational LL team, are fully in place.</p> <p>A strategic roadmap outlining envisioned strategies and expected impacts has been developed and is used to steer LL activities over time. In parallel, a business plan/model have been established, covering key activities, cost structures, and emerging revenue streams. While some business model components (such as customer segments and revenue streams) are still being refined, the overall structure is operational and supports the long-term sustainability of the LL beyond individual projects.</p>	

The LL benefits from access to appropriate infrastructure and equipment, including co-creation spaces, testing environments, and digital tools that enable participatory processes, experimentation, and stakeholder engagement.

The governance and strategic development of the LL are characterised by strong multi-actor collaboration. Actors from government, the private sector, academia, and civil society are actively involved in governance structures, contributing to decision-making and strategic orientation. While formal partner agreements are not in place for all actors, sustained and structured involvement across the quadruple helix is evident.

This collaborative culture supports shared ownership of the LL's mission and reinforces alignment between research, practice, policy, and societal needs.

Meso-level Assessment: Projects, Operations, and Resources

As of February 2026, the Green Point F2F Living Lab has completed or is currently implementing seven LL projects, with a target of eleven projects to be achieved by August 2027. These projects align with the LL's mission and contribute to innovation, co-creation, and stakeholder engagement within the regional agri-food system.

Projects cover a range of thematic areas, including sustainable production practices, processing and market innovation, food system governance, and stakeholder engagement activities. Outcomes are documented and shared, contributing to collective learning within the LL and across the legumES project. Planned participation in AGROECOLOGY Network is expected to further expand the LL's scope and strengthen its network.

The LL has a well-established operational team, with key roles fully allocated. These include a LL manager, project managers, pilot managers, researchers specialising in human interaction and co-creation, community and panel managers, and communication staff. This allocation supports the effective planning, facilitation, and implementation of LL activities.

Access to infrastructure and equipment is generally regular to continuous. Office spaces, testing facilities, and network spaces are available on a regular basis, while co-creation materials and digital communication and collaboration tools (e.g. online platforms for interaction and co-design) are continuously accessible. This ensures that LL projects can be implemented flexibly and responsively in real-life settings.

Micro-level Assessment: Co-creation Activities and User Engagement

At the micro level, the Green Point F2F LL demonstrates a strong commitment to iterative and reflexive co-creation processes. Users and stakeholders are involved almost always (>75% of activities) across all phases of the innovation cycle, including problem identification, solution design and development, testing, evaluation, demonstration, and implementation.

The LL applies iterative processes that integrate feedback from stakeholders at multiple stages, allowing innovations to be continuously refined based on real-life experience. Tools and methods are used to capture feedback, support learning, and adapt processes accordingly. Reflexive

monitoring is embedded as a core principle, enabling the LL to adjust roles, methods, and processes in response to changing contexts.

Ethical and data protection considerations are addressed through the appointment of a data protection officer and the presence of an ethics oversight mechanism for LL activities.

Stakeholder engagement within the LL is broad and diverse, spanning government (local and national), funding agencies, private sector actors (including SMEs and sector organisations), academia (universities, research centres, and students), and civil society (NGOs and communities of users). In total, eleven different stakeholder categories have been actively involved in LL activities over the past year.

As of February 2026, the LL has implemented approximately 14 stakeholder engagement activities, with a target of 28 activities to be achieved by August 2027. These activities include workshops, co-creation sessions, networking events, and participatory consultations that facilitate meaningful interaction and collaboration.

Users and stakeholders are not only informed or consulted but are actively involved and empowered across all phases of the LL innovation cycle. Their influence extends from problem identification to implementation, ensuring that solutions are grounded in real-world needs and jointly shaped by relevant actors.

Feedback-capturing measures are systematically applied, with 6 measures implemented by February 2026 and a target of 18 by August 2027. These mechanisms support continuous improvement and help assess stakeholder satisfaction, perceived influence, and learning outcomes.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

Overall, as of February 2026, the Green Point F2F LL demonstrates an advanced level of maturity, particularly with regard to governance structures, stakeholder engagement, and the systematic application of iterative co-creation processes in real-life settings. Areas for continued development include the further refinement of the business model, particularly in relation to customer segmentation and revenue streams, as well as the continued scaling and consolidation of LL projects. These aspects are expected to progress through ongoing project activities and targeted capacity-building actions within WP1 of legumES. The final evaluation in August 2027 will assess how these elements have evolved over time and will provide a comprehensive assessment of LL maturity and sustainability.

3.3.2. AgKu

Table 3: LL Assessment Results – AgKu (February 2026)

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	LegumES Hungary Living Lab
Host Organisation	Agri Kulti Nonprofit Ltd
Geographical Location	Throughout Hungary
Sector(s) of Focus	Agriculture – primarily food production, food processing, hospitality (restaurants) and public catering
Main Mission of the LL	(Re)developing the value chain of legumes grown for human consumption in Hungary from seed to fork
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENoLL) 	Active/Operational LL (not ENoLL but part of the Agroecology Network of Living Labs)
Living Lab Assessment	
Macro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Constellation	
<p>At the macro level, the legumES Hungary LL demonstrates a clear strategic orientation with several governance elements still under development. A shared vision and mission are already in place and guide the LL’s activities, particularly around rebuilding legume-based value chains for human consumption.</p> <p>Strategic decision-making processes are established, allowing the LL to prioritise activities and align projects with its mission. At the same time, key governance components, such as a formal governance structure and a strategic roadmap, are currently under development. These elements are expected to be further formalised as the LL consolidates its operational experience and expands its project portfolio.</p> <p>A fully articulated business plan or business model is currently missing, reflecting the LL’s ongoing transition from project-driven activities toward a more structured and sustainable LL setup. Nevertheless, an operational LL team is in place, and the LL benefits from access to core infrastructure and facilities, including testing environments and co-creation materials. Some equipment and digital tools supporting co-creation are still being further developed.</p> <p>The LL’s culture is characterised by strong collaboration with private sector actors, academia, and civil society, particularly in shaping the LL’s vision and mission. While stakeholders are actively involved in</p>	

strategic discussions, formal partner agreements and structured governance roles for external actors are not yet established.

Public authorities are currently less involved at governance level, indicating an area for potential strengthening in future development phases. Overall, collaboration is driven primarily by shared thematic interests and project-based cooperation rather than formalised governance arrangements.

Meso-Level Assessment: Living Lab Projects and Operations

As of February 2026, the legumES Hungary LL has completed one project and is currently implementing two additional projects, with two further projects planned to commence later in 2026. This results in a projected total of five to seven LL projects by August 2027.

The completed project (TRUE) played a catalytic role by initiating on-farm cultivation trials and effectively kickstarting the LL. Ongoing projects, including DIVINFOOD and legumES, have contributed to consolidating the LL as a functional environment for multi-actor collaboration. Planned participation in AGROECOLOGY and PROCEED is expected to further expand the LL's scope and strengthen its network.

The LL has several key operational roles fully allocated, including a LL manager, human interaction specialist, pilot manager, and project manager. Communication capacity is partially allocated, while a dedicated panel or community manager role is currently not assigned.

This configuration allows the LL to operate effectively at its current scale but also highlights areas where additional capacity, particularly for community management and structured stakeholder engagement, could further strengthen LL operations.

Access to infrastructure and tools is mixed but generally sufficient for current activities. Testing facilities and co-creation materials are regularly or continuously available, while office spaces and network spaces are accessed on a more irregular basis. Digital communication tools are continuously available, and co-creation platforms and experimentation devices are regularly accessible.

This reflects a LL that is functional and adaptable, but still reliant on flexible and project-based access to infrastructure.

Micro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Activities and Co-Creation Processes

At the micro level, the legumES Hungary LL applies iterative and reflexive processes across its projects, with a strong emphasis on adapting activities based on real-life contexts and stakeholder feedback. Iterative co-creation and experimentation are explicitly used, and lessons learned are captured in a reflective manner.

Reflexive monitoring is recognised as a key principle, and the LL demonstrates the capacity to adjust roles and processes in response to changing circumstances. A data protection officer has been appointed, ensuring compliance with data protection requirements. However, a formal ethics committee overseeing LL activities is not yet in place, representing an area for future development.

Stakeholder engagement within the LL is diverse and balanced, involving actors from government (local level), the private sector (industry, SMEs, and sector organisations), academia (universities, research centres, and students), and civil society (NGOs, think tanks, user communities, and open innovation arrangements).

As of February 2026, the LL has implemented approximately 10–15 stakeholder engagement activities since the start of legumES, with a target of 20–30 activities to be achieved by August 2027. These activities include multi-actor workshops, co-creation and validation workshops, farmer-focused workshops (both online and offline), dissemination events, and focus groups.

Users and stakeholders exert meaningful influence across most phases of the innovation cycle, particularly in problem identification, stakeholder integration, solution design and development, testing, evaluation, demonstration, and implementation. Their role generally ranges from active involvement to collaboration, reflecting a strong user-centric orientation.

Feedback-capturing measures are applied systematically, with approximately 6–7 measures implemented since the start of legumES and a target of 12–14 measures to be achieved by August 2027. These include surveys, reflection forms, interviews, and focus group discussions, supporting continuous learning and adaptation.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

As of February 2026, the LegumES Hungary LL can be characterised as a functioning and practice-oriented LL in a consolidation phase. It demonstrates strong engagement in real-life experimentation, iterative co-creation, and value-chain-oriented innovation, particularly in relation to legumes for human consumption.

Key strengths include its project portfolio, stakeholder diversity, and practical application of MAA principles at activity level. Areas for further development include the formalisation of governance structures, the development of a comprehensive business model, increased involvement of public authorities at governance level, and the establishment of formal ethical oversight mechanisms.

These aspects are expected to be progressively addressed through ongoing and planned projects and through capacity-building activities foreseen within WP1 of legumES. The final evaluation in August 2027 will assess how these governance, sustainability, and institutionalisation elements have evolved over time.

3.3.3. APRI

Table 4: LL Assessment Results – APRI (February 2026)

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	BiodivRURAL: Farmland biodiversity for rural wellbeing
Host Organisation	Asociación Aprisco de Las Corchuelas
Geographical Location	Cáceres province, North of Extremadura (Spain)
Sector(s) of Focus	Conservation and promotion of biodiversity on productive land (e.g. crop diversification) and Knowledge transfer on this topic
Main Mission of the LL	Promote agroecology research in the region and use field studies as a learning environment for different segments of the local population.
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENoLL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active/Operational LL (not ENoLL but part of the Agroecology Network of Living Labs)
LL Assessment	
Macro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Constellation <p>At the macro level, the BiodivRURAL LL demonstrates a well-established mission and a partially formalised governance structure. A shared vision and mission are clearly in place and actively guide LL activities. Governance structures exist and are operational, although some elements remain under development, indicating an adaptive and evolving organisational setup.</p> <p>Strategic decision-making processes and a strategic roadmap are currently under development, reflecting an ongoing effort to formalise longer-term strategic planning and clarify expected impacts. Similarly, the LL’s business plan and business model, including value propositions, cost structures, and revenue streams, are under development. This is consistent with the LL’s strong orientation toward publicly funded research and community-based agroecological initiatives, rather than market-driven service provision at this stage.</p> <p>The LL has an operational team in place and access to core infrastructure. Testing facilities are continuously available, while co-creation spaces, office facilities, and digital tools are accessible on a regular basis. Equipment supporting co-creation and experimentation is still being strengthened, particularly in relation to digital platforms and devices.</p> <p>BiodivRURAL exhibits a strong culture of collaboration, particularly with private sector actors, academia, and civil society. These actors are actively involved in the governance structure of the LL,</p>	

contributing to strategic discussions and decision-making processes. Government actors are primarily involved in shaping the shared vision and mission rather than in formal governance roles.

While formal partner agreements are not widely established, collaboration is structured and sustained through ongoing projects, shared activities, and long-term relationships within the regional agroecological ecosystem. This reflects a LL model grounded in trust-based cooperation and place-based engagement.

Meso-Level Assessment: Living Lab Projects and Operations

As of February 2026, the BiodivRURAL LL is implementing two LL projects, with a target of six projects by August 2027. These projects align closely with the LL's objectives of biodiversity conservation, agroecological research, and rural knowledge exchange. Projects are designed to contribute to innovation, co-creation, and stakeholder engagement, using real-life field studies as experimental and learning environments. The planned expansion of the project portfolio reflects a clear ambition to scale LL activities over the remaining project period.

The LL operates with a partially allocated team structure. Key roles, including LL manager, researchers, community and panel managers, project managers, and communicators, are partially allocated, while the pilot manager role is fully allocated. This configuration enables the LL to function effectively but also indicates reliance on shared roles and limited dedicated capacity.

Further strengthening of human resources, particularly in coordination and communication roles, would support the scaling and institutionalisation of LL activities.

Infrastructure and equipment availability is uneven but sufficient for current activities. Testing facilities are continuously available, reflecting the LL's strong grounding in field-based experimentation. Office spaces, network spaces, and communication platforms are regularly accessible. Co-creation materials are continuously available, while digital co-creation platforms and experimentation devices are either irregularly accessible or currently missing.

This reflects a LL that is highly effective in physical, field-based contexts, with digital infrastructure representing a potential area for future development.

Micro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Activities and Co-Creation Processes

At the micro level, BiodivRURAL demonstrates a strong commitment to iterative and reflexive LL processes. Iterative co-creation, experimentation, and evaluation are systematically applied, and innovations are refined based on stakeholder feedback. Lessons learned are captured throughout project execution, and reflexive monitoring is embedded as a guiding principle.

The LL shows a high capacity to adapt roles and processes in response to changing circumstances and real-life conditions. However, while ethical reflection is present in practice, a formal ethics committee and a designated data protection officer are not yet in place, representing areas for further formalisation.

Users and stakeholders are almost always involved (>75% of activities) in key phases such as problem identification, stakeholder integration, and implementation of solutions. For other phases, including solution development, testing, evaluation, and demonstration, user involvement is regular (50–75% of activities). Solution design is less formalised as a distinct phase, suggesting that design and experimentation are often integrated within field-based activities.

The LL engages a broad and diverse range of stakeholders, spanning local and regional governments, funding agencies, SMEs and sector organisations, academia (universities, schools, research centres, and students), NGOs, and communities of citizens. In total, eleven stakeholder categories have been actively involved in LL activities over the last year.

As of February 2026, the LL has implemented 12 stakeholder engagement activities, with a target of 40 activities to be achieved by August 2027. These activities include workshops, co-creation sessions, networking events, public consultations, and other participatory initiatives.

Stakeholders exert high levels of influence across the innovation cycle, frequently reaching the level of collaboration or empowerment, particularly in problem identification, testing, demonstration, and implementation of solutions. This reflects a strong user-centric orientation consistent with agroecological and community-based research traditions.

The LL has implemented 24 feedback-capturing measures by February 2026, with an ambitious target of 30 measures by August 2027. These include surveys, reflection forms, interviews, and focus group reflections, supporting systematic assessment of stakeholder satisfaction, learning, and perceived influence.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

As of February 2026, the BiodivRURAL LL can be characterised as a mature, place-based LL with strong practical and social embedding, particularly in agroecological research and biodiversity-focused field experimentation. Its strengths lie in deep stakeholder engagement, real-life experimentation, and reflexive learning processes.

Key areas for further development include the formalisation of strategic planning and governance structures, strengthening of the business model, enhancement of digital co-creation infrastructure, and the establishment of formal ethical and data protection mechanisms. Addressing these areas will support the long-term sustainability and scalability of the LL.

These developments are expected to progress through ongoing and planned activities and through capacity-building actions supported within WP1 of legumES. The final evaluation in August 2027 will assess how these elements have evolved and how the LL's maturity and institutionalisation have progressed over time.

3.3.4. AGFT

Table 5: LL Assessment Results – AGFT (February 2026)

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	RAMAS
Host Organisation	AGFUTURA TECHNOLOGIES
Geographical Location	Skopje, N. Macedonia
Sector(s) of Focus	Digital agriculture and agronomy
Main Mission of the LL	Improvement of the agricultural production system by the introduction of digital technologies and contemporary agronomy knowledge
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENoLL) 	Pilot stage: has been initiated through the development of the Remote Agricultural Monitoring and Advisory System (RAMAS), supported by the Fund for Innovation and Technology Development and the Horizon Europe CODECS project.
LL Assessment	
Macro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Constellation <p>At the macro level, the RAMAS LL demonstrates a clear thematic vision but an early-stage organisational structure. A shared vision and mission are already defined and provide strategic direction for LL development. However, most governance-related elements are either planned or under development, reflecting the LL’s pilot-stage maturity.</p> <p>Formal governance structures (such as steering or advisory bodies) are planned but not yet established. Strategic roadmapping and strategic decision-making processes are under development, indicating an ongoing transition from project-based innovation activities toward a more structured LL framework. At this stage, a comprehensive business plan or business model, covering activities, cost structures, and revenue streams, is currently missing.</p> <p>While a fully operational LL team has not yet been formally constituted, the LL benefits from access to infrastructure and equipment that support technical development and piloting activities, particularly testing facilities and digital experimentation tools. These resources provide a technical foundation upon which LL governance and operations can be built.</p> <p>Despite its early stage, RAMAS already engages a diverse set of stakeholders. Government and societal actors have contributed to shaping the LL’s vision and mission, while private sector and academic actors are involved in governance-related discussions. Collaboration is currently driven primarily through project-based and informal arrangements rather than formalised partnership agreements.</p>	

This configuration reflects a LL that is network-oriented and exploratory, with stakeholder relationships forming around concrete technical and innovation challenges rather than established governance mechanisms.

Meso-Level Assessment: Living Lab Projects and Operations

As of February 2026, the RAMAS LL does not yet count any formal LL projects under its portfolio, besides legumES. However, one additional LL project is planned, which is expected to operationalise the LL approach more explicitly through structured co-creation, testing, and validation activities.

The current phase is therefore best described as pre-operational, focusing on technical system development, concept validation, and the preparation of LL processes rather than on the execution of multiple LL projects.

Human resource allocation reflects the LL's early-stage status. Key roles such as LL manager, project managers, community managers, and communicators are currently not allocated, while several roles (e.g. researcher and pilot manager) are planned but not yet assigned.

This indicates a clear recognition of the roles required for LL operation, even though dedicated capacity has not yet been mobilised. The gradual allocation of these roles is expected as the LL transitions from pilot development to operational implementation.

Infrastructure availability is uneven but sufficient for pilot-stage activities. Testing facilities and co-creation materials are regularly accessible, supporting technical experimentation. Office spaces, network spaces, and digital co-creation platforms are currently limited or not available, while communication tools are used irregularly.

Overall, the LL infrastructure is oriented toward technical testing rather than participatory co-creation at this stage, which is consistent with the LL's current focus.

Micro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Activities and Co-Creation Processes

At the micro level, RAMAS shows initial elements of reflexive practice, particularly in capturing lessons learned and adjusting roles and processes in response to changing circumstances. However, most core LL principles, such as iterative co-creation cycles, reflexive monitoring, and systematic feedback integration, are not yet fully applied.

Formal mechanisms for ethics oversight and data protection are currently missing, reflecting the early developmental stage of the LL.

User and stakeholder involvement is present but limited in scope. Engagement occurs regularly (50–75% of activities) in phases such as problem identification, stakeholder integration, solution design, development, testing, demonstration, and implementation. Evaluation activities involve stakeholders less frequently.

This indicates that stakeholder involvement is currently focused on technical validation and piloting, rather than on fully iterative co-creation across all innovation phases.

Despite its early-stage maturity, RAMAS has engaged a remarkably broad range of stakeholder groups, including local, regional, national, and international public authorities, funding agencies, SMEs, sector organisations, universities, schools, students, and NGOs. This breadth reflects strong networking capacity and relevance within the digital agriculture ecosystem.

By February 2026, approximately 5 stakeholder engagement activities have been carried out, with a target of 10 activities by August 2027. These activities include workshops, consultations, and technical engagement events linked to digital agriculture and advisory system development.

Stakeholder influence across the innovation cycle ranges from involvement to collaboration, particularly in problem identification, solution development, testing, demonstration, and implementation. Other phases, such as solution design and evaluation, are less developed in terms of participatory influence.

Feedback-capturing measures are currently limited, with one measure implemented by February 2026 and a target of 3 measures to be achieved by August 2027. This reflects the LL's current emphasis on system development rather than structured stakeholder feedback processes.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

As of February 2026, the RAMAS LL can be characterised as a technically driven, pilot-stage LL with strong innovation potential, particularly in the domain of digital agriculture and agronomy. Its main strengths lie in its clear technological vision, broad stakeholder reach, and access to testing facilities.

Key development needs include the formalisation of governance structures, allocation of dedicated LL roles, establishment of participatory co-creation processes, and strengthening of feedback and ethical oversight mechanisms. These steps are essential for transitioning from a technology-centred pilot initiative to a fully operational LL aligned with MAA principles.

Support from WP1 capacity-building activities and continued engagement through legumES are expected to play a critical role in advancing the LL's maturity by the final evaluation in August 2027.

3.3.5. JHI

JHI contributes to legumES through two distinct but complementary LL configurations, which differ in maturity and scope and are therefore assessed separately in this interim evaluation.

- (i) The Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform is a well-established research infrastructure operating since 2009. Although not originally designed as a LL, it already exhibits many LL characteristics and is currently being aligned with LL principles within legumES, with the ambition to formalise it as a LL.
- (ii) In parallel, the legumES farm trials represent a project-specific and emerging LL configuration, focused on on-farm experimentation and legume valorisation. At M26, this configuration remains at a concept to early pilot stage, with LL elements being progressively introduced.

Table 6: LL Assessment Results – JHI (1) (February 2026).

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform
Host Organisation	The James Hutton Institute
Geographical Location	Eastern Scotland
Sector(s) of Focus	Farming, legume-based regenerative systems
Main Mission of the LL	To promote regenerative cropping practices for multiple benefits
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENOLL) 	Active/operational LL: operating since 2009 as an institute resource, with the intention to further align with the LL principles and register as a formal LL
LL Assessment	
Macro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Constellation <p>At the macro level, Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform demonstrates a high level of maturity in governance and strategic orientation, reflecting its long-standing institutional embedding. A shared vision and mission are clearly defined and actively guide platform activities. Formal governance structures and strategic decision-making processes are in place, supported by a strategic roadmap outlining long-term research objectives and expected impacts.</p> <p>An operational LL team is fully established, and it benefits from well-developed physical infrastructure and testing facilities that support long-term experimentation in real-life farming conditions. While a dedicated business plan or business model is still under development, this</p>	

reflects the platform's primary role as a research infrastructure rather than a service-oriented LL at this stage.

LL equipment and digital tools are partially under development, indicating opportunities to further strengthen participatory and co-creation capacities, particularly in relation to stakeholder interaction and feedback mechanisms.

The collaboration model is characterised by strong academic and private-sector engagement, particularly in shaping the platform's vision and mission. Government and societal actors are primarily involved through informal participation rather than through formal governance roles.

This configuration reflects a research-driven LL constellation with established scientific credibility, while also highlighting potential for deeper and more structured multi-actor governance as the platform transitions further toward a LL model.

Meso-Level Assessment: Living Lab Projects and Operations

As of February 2026, Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform is running one LL project alongside legumES. This project focuses on testing and demonstrating a legume-based crop rotation within a regenerative arable cropping system, designed to optimise soil health, biodiversity, and crop yields while minimising reliance on agrochemical inputs, particularly mineral fertilisers.

The platform's long-term experimental nature provides a strong foundation for expanding the LL project portfolio over time, although target values for the number of future projects are still to be defined.

It benefits from a well-established human resource structure. Key roles, including LL manager and researchers with human interaction specialist, are fully allocated. Several operational roles, such as panel or community manager, pilot manager, project manager, and communicator, are partially allocated, reflecting shared responsibilities within the institute. This configuration supports effective operation at current scale, while indicating potential benefits from more dedicated capacity for stakeholder engagement and communication as LL activities expand.

Infrastructure availability is strong and reliable, particularly with regard to testing facilities and experimentation devices, which are continuously accessible. Office spaces and communication platforms are regularly available, supporting day-to-day operations.

However, network spaces, co-creation materials, and digital co-creation platforms are currently limited or not available. This suggests that the infrastructure is optimised for experimental research, with scope to further develop spaces and tools that support participatory co-creation and interaction with external actors.

Micro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Activities and Co-Creation Processes

Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform applies iterative and reflexive research processes throughout its activities. Iteration based on stakeholder feedback is evident, and lessons

learned are captured in a reflective manner. It demonstrates openness to adapting research processes in response to real-life conditions and embeds reflexive monitoring as a guiding principle.

At the same time, formal structures for ethics oversight and data protection specific to LL activities are not yet established.

User and stakeholder involvement varies across stages of the innovation cycle. While activities such as testing, demonstration, and implementation of solutions are carried out without direct user involvement, other stages, such as stakeholder integration and solution design, show more regular engagement.

Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform engages a focused but relevant set of stakeholders, including national-level public authorities, funding agencies, universities, research centres, and students. Engagement with private sector actors, NGOs, and citizen communities is currently limited. By February 2026, it has implemented one stakeholder engagement activity, with a target of five activities to be achieved by August 2027.

Stakeholder influence across the innovation cycle generally ranges from consultation to involvement, particularly in problem identification, solution development, testing, evaluation, demonstration, and implementation. More advanced forms of collaboration or empowerment are not yet systematically applied.

Feedback-capturing mechanisms are currently limited, with no formal measures implemented yet and a target of two measures to be achieved by August 2027. Strengthening these mechanisms will support more structured learning and stakeholder reflection within LL activities.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

As of February 2026, the Centre for Sustainable Cropping can be characterised as a highly mature experimental platform that is transitioning toward a LL model. Its key strengths lie in long-term infrastructure, scientific excellence, and robust experimental capacity in regenerative and legume-based cropping systems.

To further consolidate its LL character, Centre for Sustainable Cropping would benefit from strengthening participatory co-creation processes, expanding stakeholder engagement beyond the research and policy domains, and formalising feedback, ethics, and data governance mechanisms. These developments are expected to be supported through legumES activities and WP1 capacity-building actions.

The final evaluation in August 2027 will assess how effectively the LL has progressed in translating its strong research foundation into a fully operational LL aligned with MAA principles.

Table 7: LL Assessment Results – JHI (2) (February 2026)

Category	Information
LL Name (if existing)	legumES farm trials
Host Organisation	The James Hutton Institute
Geographical Location	Eastern Scotland
Sector(s) of Focus	Farming, on-farm legume use
Main Mission of the LL	To promote crop diversification and valorisation
Status of the LL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept Stage (The LL is in the initial planning or concept phase) • Pilot Stage (The LL is conducting early-stage testing or pilot projects) • Active/Operational LL (The LL is fully operational, but may not yet be formally registered) • Registered LL (The LL is officially registered as a member of ENOLL) 	Concept stage – interest in moving to pilot stage will be assessed as farm trials progress
LL Assessment	
<p>Macro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Constellation</p> <p>At the macro level, the legumES farm trials Living Lab shows limited formalisation. A shared vision and mission are planned but not yet in place, and core governance elements, such as governance structures, strategic roadmaps, decision-making processes, and business models, are currently missing.</p> <p>An operational team is partially allocated, reflecting reliance on existing project staff. Infrastructure and equipment specific to LL operation are not yet established, indicating that the configuration currently functions primarily as a project-based experimental setup.</p> <p>Collaboration at this stage is narrow and project-driven. Private sector and academic actors are involved through existing partnerships, while government and societal actors are engaged informally or not yet involved. This reflects the early exploratory nature of the LL configuration.</p>	
<p>Meso-Level Assessment: Living Lab Projects and Operations</p> <p>As of February 2026, the legumES farm trials LL includes two projects: one ongoing project legumES focused on market valorisation of legume crops, and one completed project (DIVERSify/SEAMS) addressing cereal–legume intercropping and processing. These projects provide a practical foundation for LL development but are not yet organised under a coherent LL framework.</p> <p>Human resource allocation is limited and partial. Key roles such as LL manager, human interaction specialist, and data analyst are planned but not yet assigned, while pilot management, project management, and communication roles are partially allocated.</p>	

Access to infrastructure and tools is limited. Office spaces, testing facilities, network spaces, co-creation materials, and digital co-creation platforms are largely unavailable. Communication tools are used on a regular basis, and experimentation devices are accessible irregularly.

Micro-Level Assessment: Living Lab Activities and Co-Creation Processes

The legumES farm trials LL demonstrate early elements of iterative practice, particularly through openness to real-life contexts and iterative refinement of research activities. However, reflexive monitoring, systematic feedback integration, and formal learning mechanisms are not yet fully embedded. No formal ethics oversight or data protection roles specific to LL activities are currently in place.

User and stakeholder involvement is irregular and phase-specific. Engagement occurs primarily during stakeholder integration and testing phases, while involvement in problem identification, solution design, development, and implementation remains limited. Evaluation activities involve stakeholders more consistently, reflecting a research-led rather than co-creation-led approach at this stage.

Stakeholder engagement remains narrow but relevant, involving national-level public authorities, funding agencies, SMEs, research centres, and students. Broader involvement of civil society actors and user communities is currently absent.

As of February 2026, the LL has implemented two stakeholder engagement activities, with a target of five activities by August 2027. Engagement activities are primarily linked to project dissemination and consultation rather than structured co-creation.

Stakeholder influence across the innovation cycle is generally limited to consultation, with some involvement during testing and evaluation phases. More advanced levels of collaboration or empowerment are not yet observed.

Feedback-capturing measures are at an early stage, with one measure implemented by February 2026 and a target of three measures to be achieved by August 2027. These mechanisms provide an initial basis for reflection but are not yet systematically applied.

Interim Summary and Development Outlook

As of February 2026, the legumES farm trials LL can be characterised as an emerging LL configuration, primarily oriented toward on-farm experimentation rather than structured multi-actor co-creation. Its main strengths lie in its practical experimental foundation and its integration within broader research projects at JHI.

Key development needs include the articulation of a shared vision, establishment of basic governance structures, allocation of dedicated LL roles, and expansion of stakeholder engagement and feedback mechanisms. Progress in these areas will determine whether the configuration evolves toward a pilot-stage LL over the remaining project period. The final evaluation in August

2027 will assess whether the legumES farm trials LL have transitioned from a project-based setup into a more formalised LL aligned with MAA principles.

Support from WP1 activities within legumES is expected to play a central role in this transition. In particular, guidance on LL governance, application of the MAA and capacity-building activities will support the structuring and maturation of the LL. In parallel, ongoing legumES project activities, including farm trials and stakeholder engagement actions will provide practical opportunities to embed LL principles incrementally as the project progresses.

Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the interim evaluation of the implementation of the MAA within the legumES project in February 2026, with a particular focus on the development and functioning of LLs as structured environments for co-creation and experimentation.

At project level, the assessment confirms that MAA-related engagement activities are implemented across multiple WPs and involve a diverse range of stakeholders. Engagement formats include workshops, participatory trials, consultations, and co-creation processes. While the depth and intensity of engagement vary across activities, the findings indicate that the MAA is operationalised both strategically and within PS implementation processes. In several cases, engagement extends beyond consultation and involves active collaboration, reflecting the presence of genuine actor participation in experimentation and knowledge exchange.

At the LL level, the evaluation demonstrates differentiated levels of maturity among participating LLs. Some LLs operate as established and structured environments with defined governance and ongoing experimentation activities, while others are in phases of consolidation or exploration. The February 2026 assessment captures the current stage of development of participating LLs, particularly in relation to governance structures, stakeholder engagement, and co-creation practices, and establishes a baseline for monitoring their evolution.

Overall, the interim evaluation confirms that the MAA is embedded within legumES, while also highlighting areas for further structuring and consolidation, particularly in governance formalisation, systematic feedback mechanisms, and long-term sustainability planning of LLs. The findings establish a reference point for the final evaluation in August 2027, which will assess the evolution of LLs and MAA-related engagement practices throughout the project duration.

References

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- [2] European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). (n.d.). *What are Living Labs?* Available at: <https://enoll.org/living-labs/> (Accessed: 10.02.2026).
- [3] European Commission (2024). *Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” – Implementation of Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses*. Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7d4bea74-a238-11ef-85f0-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> (Accessed: 10.02.2026).

Annex 1: legumES LL Trainings for PS Leads up until February 2026 (M26)

Training Nr.	Training	Topic	Time
#1	Introductory Workshop on LLs	Introduction to the topic, setting foundational concepts, and introducing key terms. Supported by an external expert from the project NBSOIL.	20/03/2025
#2	LL Set-up Session	Interactive session at the 2nd GA to support emerging LLs with practical exercises for their development. Participants identified key foundations, current status, challenges, and stakeholders. Interactive tools and templates were provided to interested Pilot Leads for outlining next steps.	25/03/2025
#3	LL Governance Framework	Introducing Pilot Leads to the developed governance framework for legumES LLs and its main elements.	24/06/2025

**Ongoing training sessions will be delivered over the course of the project to support PS leaders in fully adopting and operationalising the LL approach*

Annex 2: LL self-assessment questionnaire Template

MACRO-LEVEL - the Living Lab constellation:

Governance & Business Model

1) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an “X” the status¹ of each governance element for your Living Lab at this point. **The goal is to progress each element to the highest level of development within the Living Lab by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

	In Place	In Development	Planned for but Not Started	Currently missing
A shared vision/mission	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A governance structure (e.g., steering committee, management structure...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A strategic roadmap describing the envisioned strategies and their expected impacts	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Strategic decision-making processes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A Business Plan/Model, including key activities, revenue streams and cost structure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
An operational Living Lab team (<i>executing Living Lab projects and activities</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Living Lab infrastructures (e.g., offices, co-creation spaces, testing facilities...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Living Lab equipment (hard- and software) (e.g., co-creation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/survey software...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an “X” the status of each business model element for your Living Lab at this point. **The goal is to progress each element to the highest level of development within the Living Lab in order to have a comprehensive and fully developed business model by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

¹ **In Place** => Fully implemented, actively used, and functioning as intended; **In Development** => Implementation has started, with partial functionality in place. Some elements are operational, but further work is needed; **Planned but Not Started** => A formal decision has been made to implement, but no concrete steps have been taken yet; **Currently Missing** => Not in place, and there are no concrete plans for its implementation at this stage

	In Place	In Development	Planned for but Not Started	Currently missing
Value proposition(s) (solutions and services offered to solve problems)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Key activities (overview of activities performed by the Living Lab, e.g., co-creation workshops, events, survey...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Customer segments (overview of possible clients paying for the services/solutions of the Living Lab)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
User segments (overview of groups of people needed to be involved in Living Lab activities)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Key resources (overview of the necessary items needed to run the Living Lab, e.g., co-creation space, software...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cost structure (which expenses need to be calculated for to run the Living Lab, e.g., personnel, office space...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Revenue streams (how will the Living Lab earn money, e.g., fundings, paid Living Lab services...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Culture and Collaboration

3) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an “X” what types of stakeholders are actively involved in the development of the **vision and mission**² of the Living Lab and the **governance structure**³ of the Living Lab? **The goal is to progress each stakeholder to the highest level of collaboration within the Living Lab by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

	A partner agreement is in place	Involved in the Governance Structure	Involved in the Shared Vision/Mission	Informal Participation
Government	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Private Sector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Academia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

² Stakeholders are actively involved in the mission/vision if they actively participated in the creation of it (e.g., cocreation workshops, community of practice meeting...)

³ Stakeholders are actively involved in the governance structure if they are actively participating in the strategic decision-making processes of the Living Lab (e.g., management meetings, advisory board...)

MESO-LEVEL - Living Lab project(s):

Operations

4) KPI Definition: This KPI tracks the total number of projects initiated, ongoing, or completed within the Living Lab.

KPI	Number of projects until M44.	
Measurement Technique	Number of Living Lab projects that are either running (actively being executed with allocated resources, or finished (successfully completed, with outcomes documented and shared)	
Values	Current Value at M26	Target Value
		[Please insert here your targeted value]
Comments	The project must align with the LL's objectives and contribute to innovation, co-creation, or stakeholder engagement. <i>Please provide some additional details on the LL project:</i>	

Human resources

5) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an "X" which roles have you already allocated⁴ to run the Living Lab operations. **The goal is to allocate and develop each key role to the highest level of operational readiness within the Living Lab, ensuring a well-structured and fully functional team by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration by moving roles from lower to higher levels of allocation.**

	Fully Allocated	Partially Allocated	Planned but Not Yet Assigned	Not Allocated
Living Lab Manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Researcher (human interaction specialist)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Panel and/or community manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pilot manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communicator	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (e.g., Data Analyst), namely:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

⁴ **Not Allocated** => The role has not been assigned, and there is no plan for recruitment; **Planned but Not Yet Assigned** =>The role is recognized as necessary, and recruitment or assignment is planned but not yet completed; **Partially Allocated** => The role is partially assigned, either shared between multiple individuals or covered in a limited capacity; **Fully Allocated** => The role is fully assigned to a dedicated person/team with clear responsibilities and operational engagement.

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Equipment and infrastructure

6) **Developmental Progress:** Please indicate with an “X” how frequently are the following equipment and infrastructure accessible to the Living Lab team to be used. **The goal is to have all critical resources in place and available at the highest level of accessibility within the Living Lab by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

	Continuously (>90%)	Regularly (50-90%)	Irregularly (<50%)	Not available/ not in place
Office spaces (e.g., dedicated workspaces, meeting rooms, shared desks)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Testing facilities (e.g., fab lab space, demonstration areas, experimental greenhouses...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Network spaces (e.g., spaces for co-creation, events...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Co-creation materials (e.g., flipcharts, office supplies, post-its, whiteboards, creative brainstorming kits)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication and interaction platform/tools (e.g., Mailchimp, Teams, Zoom, WhatsApp groups...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Co-creation platforms/tools (e.g., Miro, Mentimeter, Jamboard, collaborative online whiteboards...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Co-creation/experimentation devices (e.g., smartphones, iPads, computers, IoT sensors...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Openness

7) **Progress by Count:** Please indicate with an "X" which statement best reflects the current approach of your Living Lab regarding safeguarding a reflective and iterative approach to collaboration. **The goal is to ensure that the Living Lab adopts a reflective and iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration throughout its projects. By the end of the project, each statement should be reflected through practices implemented within the Living Lab. Alternatively, progress should be demonstrated by an increased number of statements being applied compared to the beginning of the project.**

Statement	
The Living Lab is using iterative processes (co-creation, exploration, experimentation, evaluation) throughout its projects. Innovations are refined based on feedback from stakeholders in the previous step(s) of the innovation cycle	<input type="checkbox"/>
The Living Lab is using tools and methods which stimulate feedback capturing and allow customers to develop their innovations in an iterative way.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Innovations are iterated based on feedback from stakeholders in the previous step(s) of the innovation cycle.	<input type="checkbox"/>
The tools and methods used by the Living Lab stimulate feedback capturing and allow customers to develop their innovations in an iterative way.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lessons learned are captured throughout the execution of Living Lab projects in a reflective way.	<input type="checkbox"/>
The research of the Living Lab is open to what is happening in the real-life context and to adjust their processes accordingly.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reflexive monitoring is one of the key principles of the Living Lab.	<input type="checkbox"/>
The Living Lab has the capability to adjust its roles and processes in response to changing circumstances.	<input type="checkbox"/>
The Living Lab has appointed a data protection officer	<input type="checkbox"/>
The Living Lab has an ethics committee that oversees and approves the activities and methodologies of its projects.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, namely:	<input type="checkbox"/>
Number of x's listed	[enter here]

MICRO-LEVEL – Living Lab activities:

Quality of the iterative LL processes in real-life settings

8) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an “X” how regularly does your Living Lab involve users/participants in their real-life context within the current Living Lab projects of your Living Lab. **The goal is to have all users/participants involved at the highest level of involvement within the Living Lab by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

	Not at all	Occasionally (<25% of all activities)	Irregularly (25-49% of all activities/steps)	Regularly (50-75% of all activities/steps)	Almost always (>75% of all activities/steps)
Problem identification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Stakeholder integration	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Solution design	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Solution development	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Testing solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Evaluating solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Demonstrating solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Implementing solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				

User-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach

9) Progress by Count: Which different types of stakeholders from your ecosystem have participated in Living Lab projects and/or activities over the last year? Please indicate with an “X” all relevant types of stakeholders involved by marking the appropriate box. **The goal is to assess the involvement of diverse stakeholder groups from each sector to ensure an inclusive, multi-actor approach within the Living Lab. By the end of the project progress should be demonstrated by an increased number of stakeholder groups being involved compared to the beginning of the project.**

QH	Stakeholder Groups	“X”
Government	Local government (e.g., city authorities)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Regional government (e.g., provinces/states)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	National government (e.g., ministries)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	International government (e.g., EU/UN)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Funding agencies (national/international)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Private Sector	Industry and large private companies	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Start-ups and SMEs	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Angel investors/Accelerator program owners	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Sector organizations and associations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Academia	Universities	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Schools	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Research centers	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Students	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Science communication centers	<input type="checkbox"/>

Society	NGOs	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Think tanks	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Community centers	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Communities of citizens/users	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Open innovation labs/arrangements (e.g., fablabs, citizen science...)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Number of x's listed		[enter here]

10) KPI Definition: This KPI monitors stakeholder engagement activities

KPI	Number of stakeholder engagement activities executed by M44 to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and co-creation within the Living Lab.	
Measurement Technique	Total number of stakeholder engagement activities carried out.	
Values	Current Value at M26	Target Value
		[Please insert here your targeted value]
Comments	Stakeholder engagement activities can include workshops, co-creation sessions, networking events, public consultations, focus groups, and other participatory initiatives. A stakeholder engagement activity is considered valid when it actively involves at least one stakeholder group in meaningful interaction, discussion, or co-creation.	

Quality of participatory tools & methods

11) Developmental Progress: Please indicate with an “X” to what extent⁵ can users/participants in your Living Lab projects exert influence on the different phases of the Living Lab innovation cycle? **The goal is to have all users/participants involved at the highest level of involvement within the Living Lab by the end of the project, or to demonstrate progress between statuses within the project duration.**

	Not involved	Informed	Consulted	Involved	Collaborated	Empowered
Problem identification						
Stakeholder integration						
Solution design						

⁵ Informed => to provide users/participants with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives and/or solutions; Consulted => to obtain users/participants feedback or analysis, alternatives and/or decision; Involve => to work directly with users/participants throughout the process to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered; Collaborated => to partner with users/participants in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution; Empowered => to place final decision-making in the hands of user/participants

Solution development						
Testing solutions						
Evaluating solutions						
Demonstrating solutions						
Implementing solutions						

12) **KPI Definition:** This KPI monitors feedback-capturing measures

KPI	Number of feedback-capturing measures implemented to assess stakeholders' satisfaction with their level of involvement, their influence on the innovation cycle, and the opportunities provided for knowledge sharing and capacity building until M44.	
Measurement Technique	Count of feedback-capturing activities conducted (e.g., surveys, reflection forms, interviews, feedback sessions).	
Values	Current Value at M26	Target Value
		[Please insert here your targeted value]
Comments	Feedback-capturing methods may include quantitative tools (e.g., Likert-scale satisfaction surveys) and qualitative tools (e.g., open feedback forms, short interviews, focus group reflections). These help assess stakeholders' perceptions of involvement, influence, and knowledge-sharing opportunities within the Living Lab activities.	